

Evaluation of Fungicidal and Bactericidal Properties of Some Fluorans and Bromofluorans

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The substituted fluorans and bromofluorans, recorded in Table I, were prepared by the method of Ghatak and Dutta (this *Journal*, 1926, 6, 465). These have then tested for fungicidal activity on *Aspergillus niger*, using potato-glucose medium and for bacteriostatic activity on *S. aureus*, using nutrient broth medium containing beef extract and peptone, by dilution method. The medium (2 c.c.) was taken in each of the 10 test tubes and sterilised. To the first tube 2 c.c. of a solution of a compound containing 0.0256 g./10 c.c. was added. This mixture (2 c.c.) was withdrawn and added to the 2nd tube and the process continued to 9th tube. The 10th tube contained only the medium. The tubes were then inoculated with 24 hours' growth culture. The concentrations of the compounds in mg./c.c., at which there was complete inhibition, are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Compound.	Colour.	M.P.	Minimum conc. (mg./c.c.) at which complete inhibition takes place.	
				<i>A. niger</i> .	<i>S. aureus</i> .
1.	4-Methyl-6-hydroxy-F	Light orange	115°	No inhibition	0.16
2.	3-Methyl-6-hydroxy-F	Chocolate	185°	Do	No inhibition
3.	2-Methyl-6-hydroxy-F	Do	175°	Do	0.32
4.	2-Chloro-6-hydroxy-F	Brownish yellow	190°	..	0.32
5.	1,3,6-Trihydroxy-F	Brown	175°	No inhibition	0.64
6.	2,6-Dihydroxy-F	Dark brown	182°	1.28.	0.64

TABLE I (contd.)

No.	Compound.	Colour.	M. P.	Minimum conc. (mg./c.c.) at which complete inhibition taken place.	
				<i>A. niger.</i>	<i>S. aureus.</i>
7.	4,5,7-Tribromo-6-hydroxy-F	Brown	205°	1.28	1.28
8.	4-Methyl-6-hydroxy-3,5,7-tribromo-F	Orange	248°	0.64	0.64
9.	2-Methyl-6-hydroxy-3,5,7-tribromo-F	Light orange	248°	0.16	0.32
10.	2-Chloro-5,7-dibromo-6-hydroxy-F	Reddish brown	200°	1.28	No inhibition
11.	4-Chloro-5,7-dibromo-6-hydroxy-F	Whitish orange	200° (decomp.)	0.64	0.64
12.	2,6-Dihydroxy-4,5-dibromo-F	Dirty yellow	180°	No inhibition	0.32
13.	1,3,6-Trihydroxy-4,5-dibromo-F	Dirty orange	218°	..	0.16

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